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Planning New Base Station Locations to Strengthen Existing Network Coverage- Application to Kestel Region

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ABSTRACT:

With the increasing population density and rising demand for mobile communication services in the Kestel District of Alanya, existing base stations are expected to fall short in providing adequate coverage. This study aims to determine the optimal locations and capacities of new base stations under limited budget constraints. The proposed methodology introduces a novel, two-stage solution framework that integrates both deterministic and scenario-based stochastic optimization models using demand-driven candidate site generation via the K-means algorithm.

In the first stage, instead of directly feeding high-resolution demand data into the model, the K-means algorithm is applied to cluster user densities, with each cluster center defined as a potential base station location. This provides a flexible, demand-oriented alternative to traditional fixed candidate locations. In the second stage, a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model based on the Maximum Coverage Problem (MCP) is developed, incorporating both macro and micro base station types.

To address demand uncertainty, scenario-based stochastic programming is employed, leading to more robust and resilient solutions. The model is implemented in Python and solved using the Gurobi optimizer. The effectiveness of the stochastic approach is evaluated using the Value of the Stochastic Solution (VSS), which demonstrates its superiority over the deterministic model.

Overall, the proposed method reduces computation time while enhancing coverage efficiency and adaptability. The approach is practical, scalable, and well-suited for urban network planning problems under uncertainty.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Due to the increasing population density and the fact that it is a touristic region in the Kestel District of Alanya, it has been determined that the existing base stations cannot meet the demand of the users due to the increase in the demand for telecommunication services and a decrease in the satisfaction of the users due to the decrease in the quality of service. It will be aimed to solve this problem by using the maximum coverage problem and the appropriate mathematical model for the problem will be established. The aim of the study is to ensure that the base stations to be installed are installed in optimum places in order to serve in accordance with the user demands in the targeted regions. Appropriate machine learning techniques will be used to identify candidate base stations. Since each demand point is a potential candidate point for base station installation, the demand points will be clustered according to the Euclidean distance by using the k-means algorithm to reduce the number, and the determined cluster centers will be used as candidate points in the mathematical model. The mathematical model will decide which base stations will be installed at the determined candidate points and which type of base station will be installed.

The maximum coverage problem used in the study is an optimization problem that aims to obtain the widest impact area with a limited number of source selections. What is important in this problem is to cover the regions where the demand is high, rather than meeting all the demands. This problem, which is encountered in many sectors, Acar [1] took advantage of the problem of maximum coverage in the selection of ammunition depots. In the literature, there are various studies on facility layout using machine learning techniques. Erradi et al. [2] used genetic algorithms and local search methods to solve the base station layout problem. Zheng et al. [3] showed that Reinforcement Learning and Graph Neural Network methods give better results compared to traditional methods in facility layout in large cities.

Selim et al. [4] in their article took the problem of placement and configuration of base stations for cellular mobile networks, focusing on the placement of base stations by optimizing cost minimization and service quality through mathematical modeling. In their study, Pei et al. [5] made base station layout planning with a genetic algorithm model developed to optimize base station locations and costs to cover more than 90% of user demands for 5G technology. In the article of Gonzalez et al. [6], it has been shown that the installation of micro base stations can be more beneficial than the installation of macro base stations in terms of energy efficiency with the mixed integer programming model and stochastic programming techniques.

In machine learning algorithms, the K-means method was used to determine the demand points and candidate points. The K-means method is a very fast clustering method that can deal with a large number of input variables and a large number of units [7]. The center points of the determined clusters will be used as base station candidate points. Çolak et al. [8] reduced 125 candidate points to 9 candidate regions by using the K-mean method in the selection of the facility location and compared the cost of the points found with the nonlinear programming method. Göçer and Şener [9] combined the multi-criteria decision-making method with the modified k-Mean algorithm in the selection of logistics centers and placed the cluster centers at the nearest candidate point with the modified k-Mean algorithm.

2. SYSTEM DEFINITION

The current layout of the base stations creates an extra demand load on the base stations in areas where users are concentrated, causing coverage gaps and low signal strength. This situation causes the signals required for the use of mobile communication devices, which are widely used in wireless communication, not to provide the same level of service for each user, thus causing service quality differences. These differences cause problems in communication and cause user grievances. The fact that base stations cannot meet the needs of users at some

points and that they are not at the desired quality signal level at some points is the basis of the problem.

Among the symptoms evaluated within the scope of the problem addressed in the project are the connection interruptions experienced by the users, the differences in the quality of service, and the overload of base stations in the areas where the users live heavily.

3. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

In this section, the stochastic optimization model developed to solve the layout problem of base stations will be detailed. The goal of the model is to maximize the actual number of users covered under uncertainty. The ambiguous parameters used in the model are: user demands and the amount of Mbps requested by each user. In addition to these uncertainties, the model was created under various constraints.

Table 1: Notation for the Mathematical Model

NOTATION	DESCRIPTION
X_{ik}	1, if i. If a type k base station is installed at the candidate point, if 0 is not installed
A_{ij}^{ω}	ω . In the script i. The number of potential customers that the base station installed at the candidate point can cover in region j.
N_j^{ω}	ω . Actual number of customers covered in region j. in scenario w.
B_k	k. Capacity of type base station
D_{ij}	i. Distance between the Candidate Base station point and j. Demand zone
R_k	k-type base station coverage radius
Q_j^{ω}	J in the script. Demand of the region ω .
T1	Maximum number of users for macro base station installation
F_k	k. Type base station cost
G	Budget
bw^{ω}	The average amount of data used by a person in the scenario ω .

In this problem, we aim to maximize the expected number of actual covered customers

$$\text{Max } z = E[\sum_j^J N_j^{\omega}]$$

(3.1)

$$\sum_{k=1}^2 x_{ik} \leq 1 \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, I\}$$

(3.2)

$$bw^\omega \cdot A_{ij}^\omega \leq \sum_{R_k \geq D_{ij}} B_k \cdot x_{ik} \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, I\}, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, J\}, \omega \in \{\omega, \dots, \Omega\}$$

(3.3)

$$\sum_{k=1}^2 B_k \cdot x_{ik} \geq \sum_{j=1}^J A_{ij}^\omega \cdot bw^\omega \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, I\} \quad \omega \in \{\omega, \dots, \Omega\}$$

(3.4)

$$\sum_{j=1}^J A_{ij}^\omega \geq T_1 + M \cdot (x_{i2} - 1) \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, I\} \quad \omega \in \{\omega, \dots, \Omega\}$$

(3.5)

$$\sum_{j=1}^J A_{ij}^\omega \leq T_1 \cdot x_{i1} + (M \cdot x_{i2}) \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, I\} \quad \omega \in \{\omega, \dots, \Omega\}$$

(3.6)

$$A_{ij}^\omega \leq \sum_{k=1}^2 Q_j^\omega \cdot x_{ik} \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, I\} \quad j \in \{1, 2, \dots, J\} \quad \omega \in \{\omega, \dots, \Omega\}$$

(3.7)

$$N_j^\omega \leq \sum_{i=1}^I A_{ij}^\omega \quad j \in \{1, 2, \dots, J\} \quad \omega \in \{\omega, \dots, \Omega\}$$

(3.8)

$$N_j^\omega \leq Q_j^\omega \quad j \in \{1, 2, \dots, J\} \quad \omega \in \{\omega, \dots, \Omega\}$$

(3.9)

$$\sum_k \sum_i x_{ik} \cdot F_k \leq G$$

(3.10)

$$x_{ik} \in \{0, 1\}$$

$$A_{ij}^\omega, N_j^\omega \geq 0$$

(3.11)

Constraint 3.2 ensures that only one type of base station will be installed at point i.

Constraint 3.3 The capacity provided by the base station installed at the candidate base station point must be sufficient to meet the data demand generated by the potential customers that can be covered in the region under scenario w.

Constraint 3.4 The total capacity of the base stations installed at the candidate point must be greater than or equal to the total data demand generated by all potential customers they can cover across all relevant regions under scenario w.

Constraint 3.5 if a micro base station is installed at candidate point i , the total number of potential customers covered by the base stations at point i across all regions j under scenario w must be greater than or equal to the maximum user capacity for a macro base station. This implies that micro base stations are intended for scenarios where the demand is high

Constraint 3.6 This constraint ensures that if a macro base station is installed at candidate point i the total number of potential customers it covers across all regions j in scenario w does not exceed its maximum user capacity (T_1). The term $M \cdot x_{i2}$ (where M is a large constant) ensures that this constraint is non-binding if a micro base station is installed ($x_{i2}=1$), allowing for higher customer coverage in that case

Constraint 3.7 The number of potential customers that the base stations installed at candidate point i can cover in region j under scenario w must be less than or equal to the total demand in region j under scenario w . This constraint ensures that the number of covered customers does not exceed the available demand in a region and that no customers are covered if no base station is installed at point i .

Constraint 3.8 For each region j and scenario w , that actual number of customers covered must be less than or equal to total number of potential customers that can be covered by all installed base stations across all candidate points i in that region

Constraint 3.9 For each region j and scenario w the actual number of customers covered cannot exceed the total demand of that region. This ensures that the system does not count more covered customers than the demand available in a region

Constraint 3.10 The total cost of the base stations to be placed should not exceed the specified budget limit

Constraint 3.11 Beacon constraints

4. METHOD

The maximum coverage problem is an optimization problem that aims to achieve the widest area of influence with a limited selection of resources [10]. Basically, it is aimed to reach the maximum number of target audiences by effectively selecting limited resources. What is important in this problem is to cover the regions where the demand is high, rather than meeting all the demands. In the model, strategic points should be selected by taking into account the coverage radius, cost, geographical obstacles, legal conditions, and road losses affecting the signal level of the base stations to be installed for maximum coverage. The purpose of the model is to maximize the actual number of customers in the region to be studied. Real customers are people who live in the area and interact with cell towers. For this purpose, there are constraints that affect the establishment of a base station. These constraints aim to install only one base station and the appropriate type of base station at each candidate base station point. Depending on the user density of the region, the appropriate base station type will be selected, and the establishment of as many base stations as necessary in line with the potential number of users of the region aims to provide benefits in terms of cost. In addition, there are assumptions used in the study: the use of 4G base stations, MIMO technology and 900mhz and 2600 mhz frequency bands in the 20 mhz spectrum width. With these features, it is assumed that the capacities of the base stations will be up to 600Mbps.

The maximum number of people to be covered by the base station must have the capacity to serve more or equal to the number of potential users in the area where it will be installed. The area covered by the base station should be optimized to meet the needs of demand zones. An

appropriate coverage radius should be selected in order to reduce the installation cost of the base station to be installed and to maximize the user benefit. This restriction is necessary to ensure that there is no degradation in signal quality. In order to provide service to a demand zone, the demand zone must be located within the coverage distance of the base station. An ideal level is determined by taking into account the signal distance and road loss values of the base station, and the demand points we want to serve should be between these points. It is planned to determine the ideal level according to the road loss analysis. The coverage distance of macro and micro base stations differs for the two types [11]. In order to decide which of the two types will be installed in a region, the population living in that region and the density of users are examined. Macro base stations are used to serve in areas where user density is low and far from each other. Micro base stations, on the other hand, are used in areas where the user density is high and close to each other. Considering this situation, it is aimed to establish macro base stations for regions below a certain user density [12]. The k-means algorithm will be used to determine the candidate base station points. After the determination of the candidate points, the mathematical modeling process will be started. In the establishment of the model, it is aimed to establish a stochastic model as a model suitable for decision-making under uncertainty due to the uncertainty of the number of potential users in the region and the variable amount of data consumed per person. As a result of the stochastic model, it will be decided which type of base station will be installed at which point. The success of the model is analyzed by calculating the value of the stochastic solution.

4.1. Solution Algorithm

- The specified parameters constitute the inputs of the study. The outputs of the study also constitute the decision variables.
- The coordinate data was retrieved from Google My Maps, exported in KML format and processed with Python.
- For the Qj parameter, it was created by multiplying the number of users at the request points and the data need per person.
- User scenarios for stochastic analysis were created using the log-normal distribution for data quantities using the poisson distribution.
- A modified K-mean algorithm weighted by demand points was applied
- The distance between each candidate point and each claim point was calculated using the Haversine formula
- The necessary parameters have been created for the scenarios
- For each scenario, the model is analyzed with the help of Gurobi and VSS is calculated.

4.2. K-Means Method

The k-means algorithm divides the data into a specified number of clusters using distance criteria [13]. The aim is to minimize the distance of the points to the cluster centers. In our study, the "Euclidean distance" method will be used to measure the distance of data points to cluster centers.

4.3. Modified K-Means Method

Unlike the classical method, the modified k-Means algorithm assigns weight values in parallel with the population density at the demand points. The weight values of the densely populated points were high, so they were further processed in the solution algorithm and the cluster centers were close to densely populated areas. The designated cluster centers can be determined

as points that are not suitable for the establishment of base stations. Şener and Göçer [9] divided 81 provinces into 15 clusters and ensured that cluster centers were placed at candidate points. The cluster centers initially determined were placed at the nearest candidate point according to the Euclidean distance. In our study, the cluster centers determined were placed on the nearest demand point and the points that are more suitable for the installation of base stations were determined.

4.3.1. Calinski-Harabasz Index

In this method, the index value is calculated by rationing the inter-set variance to the intra-cluster variance. A large index value indicates that the clusters are well separated from each other, so the highest value is chosen when determining the number of clusters [14].

$$CH(k) = \frac{tr(B_k) / (k - 1)}{tr(W_k) / (n - k)}$$

k : Number of clusters

n : Total number of observations

$tr(B_k)$: Interset variance

$tr(W_k)$: Intracluster variance

4.4. VSS

By calculating the value of the stochastic solution (VSS), the suitability of the stochastic model we mentioned earlier was tested. It is a metric used to find out how much the uncertainties added to the model contribute to the quality of the solution thanks to VSS. When it is necessary to make decisions under uncertainties, it shows how beneficial it is to integrate these uncertainties into the model.

The value of the stochastic solution is calculated on the basis of three basic concepts. These concepts illustrate the impact of uncertainty on decision-making. The recourse problem reflects the quality of the solution found by calculating it for all scenarios, taking into account the uncertainty of the stochastic model. The Expected Value Model is a deterministic model created with the expected values of random variables. When this pattern is unraveled, the decisions made usually remain constant. The expected of the expected value solution (EEV), on the other hand, is obtained by running the deterministic model under the expected value of each scenario obtained from the expected value model and accepting the x_{ik} decision variable values as constant parameters for each scenario. This measures the quality of decisions made without taking into account uncertainties. This calculation analyzes the significance level of the stochastic model. If the VSS value is close to zero, it is seen that the inclusion of uncertainties in the model does not make a significant difference in the quality of the solution. However, if the VSS value is found to be higher, it is seen that the uncertainty offers a better solution than the deterministic model.

$$VSS = \left(\frac{RP - EEV}{RP} \right) \cdot 100$$

5. RESULTS

In the study, the amount of Mbps used per capita was determined as scenarios using log-normal distribution [15]. In the stochastic model, a random structure that can take different values in each scenario has been established in order to represent variable user demands depending on the scenarios. Due to the fact that the demand cannot be negative, it is generally small but can

reach high values from time to time, it was deemed appropriate to use lognormal distribution in this study. Random data were generated by assuming that a person uses an average of 0.056 Mbps of data [16]. With the data obtained, data were produced for 50, 75, 100 and 150 scenarios.

Similarly, the variability of the number of people at the request points in the study was shaped using the poisson distribution [17]. While creating these scenarios, the number of people living at each demand point was first calculated and this number of people created the lambda value to be used in the poisson distribution. Data sets consisting of 50,75,100,150 scenarios were prepared with different lambda values determined for each demand point.

The presence of approximately 2500 candidate base station points in the region made the solution of the model practically impossible due to both calculation time and hardware limitations. Therefore, in the first step, the K-mean clustering algorithm was applied to make the dataset more manageable by reducing the number of candidate points. Based on the Euclidean distance, this algorithm divides the data into a specified number of clusters and minimizes the distances of the points to the cluster centers. In determining the number of clusters, various methods such as Elbow Method, Calinski-Harabasz Index and Silhouette Score were compared; As a result of the analyzes, the most appropriate number of clusters was determined by the Calinski-Harabasz method (Figure 1) and the obtained cluster centers were used as the final candidate base station points of the model to form the input parameters of the mathematical model. The number of 22 clusters obtained by the Calinski-Harabasz index was used in the modified K-means method and the demand points were clustered as shown in the image below (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Calinski-Harabasz Scores for Determining Optimal Cluster Number

Figure 2: K-Means Clustering Results for Demand Points in Kestel Region

When the demand points are examined, the fact that there are approximately 2500 request points, such as base station candidate points, made the solution of the model practically impossible due to both calculation time and hardware limitations. At this stage, weight values were ignored and clustering was done only according to locations. Using the K-means algorithm, the number of candidate points was reduced to 500. These points are indicated in the figure below (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Connecting Original Points to Cluster Centers

By calculating the value of the stochastic solution (VSS), the suitability of the stochastic model we mentioned earlier was tested. VSS can be used to compare the performance of the stochastic

model with the expected value problem, allowing us to infer how much the inclusion of scenario-based uncertainties improves the solution.

In the study, scenario-based stochastic programming approach was used to model the uncertainties in the number of people at the request points and the use of data per capita. Scenario-based analysis enables the examination of the results of the system under scenarios representing equal realization probabilities of uncertain parameters. Increasing the number of scenarios contributes to the model covering a wider uncertainty space and thus to producing more realistic decisions.

When the base station settlements are examined, it is seen that the same candidate points are selected in all scenarios. This result shows that regardless of the number of scenarios, certain points are consistently preferred.

The scenario-based modeling approach offers more realistic solutions to decision-makers by taking into account the uncertainties ignored by deterministic models. This approach is especially important in systems that require preparation for situations where population density is increasing or demands are uncertain. As a result, the increase in the number of scenarios not only increases the solution quality and reliability of the model, but also significantly increases the solution time and the load on the solver.

Table 2 Performance results for different scenario numbers

	Value of the Stochastic Solution	Objective Function Value	Solution Time	Established Base Station Locations	Established Base Station Type
Scenario 50	39.39	14762	574 sn	1-2-3-7-8-14-16-19-20-21	2
Scenario 75	31.86	15273	879 sn	1-2-3-7-8-14-16-19-20-21	2
Scenario 100	29.55	14986	1421 sn	1-2-3-7-8-14-16-19-20-21	2
Scenario 150	45.99	14900	2851 sn	1-2-3-7-8-14-16-19-20-21	2

The values obtained as a result of the operation of the model for each scenario are as shown in Table 2. The fact that the VSS values are at the desired level shows that the stochastic solution is meaningful. With VSS (Value of the Stochastic Solution) analysis, the effect of the stochastic model on the decision-making process was evaluated quantitatively. The VSS values in 4 different scenario values obtained in the study are given below table 2, as a result, it showed that the stochastic model was suitable for our study. In this context, it has been observed that the use of stochastic models provides more appropriate and effective results in similar studies with uncertain parameters. In line with the results obtained, it is expected to improve the coverage by installing base stations at the designated points in the region where the study is carried out.

6. CONCLUSION

In order to improve the coverage quality of the increasing population density and inadequate existing base stations in Alanya Kestel District, the optimization of the settlement with new abz stations was discussed. The problem is solved using stochastic programming under various constraints on the basis of the maximum coverage problem. K-means algorithm was used to make the number of candidate points manageable. In this way, the calculation time has been reduced and the solution has been accelerated. Priority was given to regions of high demand using the weighted K-averages method.

The model was solved with the Python Gurobi solver, and the significance of the stochastic model was calculated by calculating the value (VSS) of the stochastic solution.

When the results obtained were examined, it was seen that the coverage area could be improved by installing base stations at the determined candidate points. Thus, it has been ensured that the quality of service is maximized under limited budget and resources.

At the same time, the advantages of stochastic modeling were seen in problems with this type of uncertainty. In future studies, the scope of the study can be expanded by taking into account natural disasters, more comprehensive data sets and developing mobile communication technologies.

In this study, communication problems experienced in Alanya Kestel District due to increasing population density and insufficient coverage area of existing base stations were discussed. In order to use the existing infrastructure efficiently and to increase the service quality, it is aimed to optimize the placement of new base stations. The model developed in this direction was solved by stochastic programming method under various constraints based on the maximum coverage problem.

In order to reduce the number of candidate points to a manageable level, the K-means clustering algorithm was used, and the optimum number of clusters was determined as 22 by the Calinski-Harabasz method. With the weighted K-averages method, more realistic and effective results were obtained by giving priority to high demand regions. The model was run using the Gurobi solver in the Python environment and the significance of the model was revealed by calculating the value of the stochastic solution (VSS).

The results obtained show that the coverage area can be expanded and user satisfaction can be increased thanks to the base stations to be installed at the determined candidate points. In addition, thanks to the optimization of installation and operating costs, an economically efficient solution is offered.

The study revealed the advantages of stochastic modeling in uncertain problems. In future studies, the scope of the model can be expanded by taking into account natural disaster scenarios, broader data sets and developing mobile communication technologies.

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